

CONTENT ANALYSIS OF HARRY POTTER BOOKS SERIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8170633>

Abstract. Content analysis is a valuable research tool for social scientists that unfortunately can prove challenging to teach to undergraduate students. Published classroom exercises designed to teach content analysis have thus far been predominantly envisioned as lengthy projects for upper-level courses. A brief and engaging exercise may be more beneficial for introductory social science courses in which less time can be allotted to any one topic, such as content analysis. An evaluation study suggests that the exercise improves students' understanding of content analysis and that students find it both highly helpful and enjoyable.

Key words: Harry Potter books series, content of the book, methods of analysis, research tool, and computational analysis.

The Harry Potter series is widely known all around the world. It all started on the first of September 1998 when was the first book released. The Series was written by writer J. K. Rowling from the United Kingdom. Harry Potter became very popular for all age categories. In 2001 started movie series were filmed with books and popularity started to grow even faster. In the next years, Harry Potter became an absolute phenomenon. It started just with a book, but it created much more. According to this book series, movies, games, clothes, board games, and theme park attractions were created.

In this study, for the purpose of analyzing the Harry Potter books series, content analysis is used. Text analysis is an automated process of understanding text data and making it easier to manage. It can provide certain insights into text which are required by the user. Content analysis is widely used in processing social media, comments, survey responses, books, etc. It can be used for example for analyzing comments on some videos to find out what the comments are about or to make certain statistics about these comments. There are a lot of possibilities because we live in an age when we have much data everywhere and it is growing so fast without signs of slowing down any time soon. Everyone is commenting on something, posting, writing blogs, and sending messages. When one wants to use some of these data, (s)he wants to have it in clear and easily readable form, and that is the reason why is text analysis used.

Computational analysis of literary works is still considered as a big challenge in the field of digital literary studies, computational linguistics, machine learning, and neurocognitive poetics. Content analysis is a flourishing area which intersects linguistics and computer science. Content analysis is used to discover the sentiment contained in a text that can be assessed as positive or negative. Content analysis is the key challenge that can assess the emotional information encoded in a literary text. Although, over the last two decades, a remarkable progress has been shown in Content analysis. The progression has occurred mostly in social media for business purposes, but few researches can be found in literary works. Arthur M. Jacobs studied on sentiment analysis of poetic texts such as Shakespeare's sonnets where he focused on predicting aesthetic emotions. He also carried out Content analysis of novels such as Harry Potter book series and computed emotional and personality profiles of the protagonists. However, this type of work is rarely seen in the research domain of Content analysis. The authors have chosen this research topic considering the lack of research of Content analysis in digital literary studies.

As with all studies, this evaluation is not without limitations. In particular, the small sample size limits generalizability. Relatedly, the small sample size precluded the possibility of a control group in which only the initial lecture was provided; however, the exercise was specifically designed to include the initial minilecture because without it, the video-based exercise would lack context and purpose. Additionally, students were not asked to write out descriptions of concepts in part because their understanding of the overlap between taught concepts would have been difficult to assess in a standardized measure, but at the same time, the reliance on measures of self-reported familiarity with key concepts may possibly inflate actual concept familiarity for some students. Last, because the aim of this temporally brief exercise is to increase comprehension of content analysis rather than breadth of knowledge of or competency in conducting content analysis, the exercise's lecture component is focused on only core concepts, and students are not asked to conduct the full content analysis process. Therefore, while the exercise is well tailored for an introductory-level course, it may be less suited for upper-level courses, which may require covering the different types of content analysis and having students engage in a complete content analysis study.

Content analysis is a valuable research tool for social scientists that can prove challenging to teach to undergraduate students. This article presents a classroom exercise designed to teach students about content analysis in a highly

engaging and temporally compact manner well suited for introductory social science courses: Students are guided through a content analysis of Harry Potter film music. The evaluation reported on in this article suggests that the exercise can improve students' understanding of content analysis, and furthermore, students generally found the exercise highly helpful and enjoyable and would recommend its implementation in other courses.

A limitation to our study is lower accuracy under specific conditions. For example, finding out what a story is about in these novels was not as accurate as expected. It is not straightforward to infer the topic from the story based only on the most frequently used words. It suffices to find out which characters are the most important in each chapter and certain basic information about the chapter. For example, it was concluded that somebody died in the chapter based on the words like die, death, and kill. However, this technique was not efficient if we want to know more information about chapters. Therefore, more complex techniques such as machine learning and deep learning should be explored and implemented in future work.

The results presented in this study can be further used by marketers and decision-makers involved in any book or other kind of campaign. By showing certain statistics and sentiments related to the textual resource obtained by using text analysis, deeper insights into the quality of any kind of text including social media content can be learned and used for different purposes and domains of interest.

References:

1. Biswas, P. Exploration of Magic Realism: Harry Potter novels in perspective. *International Journal of English Language, Literature and Humanities*.
2. Bakhshilloyevna, Khamdamova Sitara. "FORMATION OF MODERN ENGLISH POETRY IN THE LATE XIX AND EARLY XX CENTURIES. *Euro-Asia Conferences*, 1 (1), 459–461." (2021).
3. Bakhshilloyevna, Khamdamova Sitara, and Yusupova Hilola Uktamovna. "SYMBOLISM IN WILLIAM BUTLER YEATS' POETRY." *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture* 2.5 (2021): 131-135.
4. Bowers, M. A. *Magic Realism*. Routledge Taylor & Francis group, London and New York, 2004.
5. Friis, C. *Abandoned Children in Literature: The Orphans in J.K. Rowling's Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone*. *Languages & Literatures*, 68 p.

6. Khamdamova, Sitora Bakhshilloyevna. "PECULIAR FEATURES OF WILLIAM BUTLER YEATS' POETRY." *Theoretical & Applied Science* 4 (2020): 348-351.
7. Khamdamova, Sitora Bakhshilloyevna. "Early period of William Butler Yeats' poetry." *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* 11.3 (2021): 1587-1591.
8. Khamdamova, Sitora B. "HARMONY OF TRADITION AND NOVELTY IN ENGLISH POETRY." *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES* 3.05 (2022): 69-72.

